

WIKI AS AN E-LEARNING TOOL AND ITS APPLICATION IN WRITING CLASSES

Abdug‘afforov Sardor

EFL teacher of NamSU

Abstract: this article defines that about wiki and using of it as an e-learning tool and its application in writing classes. Moreover there are given much information about using of wiki in writing lessons.

Key words: wiki, writing class, learning tools, using of social media.

The word wiki comes from the Hawaiian word for “fast or quick” to represent that wikis are quickly and easily created web pages. The first wiki was developed by Ward Cunningham. Wikis are one of many Web 2.0 components that can be used to enhance the learning process. Web 2.0 refers to the second generation of the internet which allows users to add and change content easily, communicate at anytime and anywhere, and develop and share information and content. Thus, wiki is a web application that can be used to allow students to add, modify or delete content within a collaborative environment. Wikis drive collaboration among students in the classroom. Furthermore, they act as a register for class activities. Wiki students can use it as a learning resource. The final product is the work of several students. Wikis have two features: read and edit. Read option allows users to read a wiki like a normal page. The edit option bottom enables users to modify and edit pages. Wikis also show a summary page that shows members contributions by showing the number of modified words and the date of modifications.

Within writing classes, wiki provides an opportunity for learners to practice writing and receive peer review and feedback. In addition, it facilitates peer revising that requires students to develop their content. Wiki allows for peer editing that requires students to check their sentence skills for correct grammar, mechanics, punctuation, and usage.

Moreover, the wiki format allows teachers to provide ongoing response to assess student performance in conjunction with peer-to-peer evaluations, and self-reflection. Therefore, wiki is a useful tool for teaching writing and can promote in students their own active role in learning writing.

Consequently, their writing motivation would be developed. All those studies agreed that wikis have been used successfully in learning and developing students' foreign languages. While PBworks promoted teamwork and significantly increased community writing standards, there seemed to be space for progress. For instance, not all students displayed strong degrees of cooperation; while some also showed no coordination at all. In comparison, observations from the interviews and questionnaires found that students still had marginally favorable attitudes towards PBworks' pedagogical importance as compared to conventional writing classrooms. This is not to suggest that the students displayed pessimistic views. Overall, even though the interview questions expressly questioned students to share their unpleasant experiences, the findings tended to be more optimistic than negative attitudes. Rather, it is possible to interpret the questionnaire and interview answers as not uniformly favorable and thus have potential for change. A potential future change may be to eliminate some barriers currently stopping certain students from making more comprehensive use of wikis, considering the wiki's beneficial function in promoting communication and writing results. One significant obstacle seemed to be the shortcomings of students in running the technology. Some reported that it was challenging to run PBworks, although others considered it inconvenient, being unused to it. Indeed, it was proposed in a recent study by Stoddart and colleagues that interactive wiki-based writing may be effectively encouraged if an instructor, who is a specialist in wiki usage, properly applied the technology to students. Teachers' competency with their own technology is considered a requirement for helping students who have challenges in operating emerging technologies. Therefore, we suggest that teachers themselves strive to sustain a reasonable degree of technical literacy. The actions of teachers and school administrators affect the usage of technology by pupils, in addition to the teacher's experience. Students' values and

aspirations are implicitly influenced by whether their mentors show their tolerance to multimedia tools for learning. In the current research, several students focused on other known applications, such as MS Word, despite technological assistance while utilizing an online tool, before uploading the result. This means that educators will need to inspire students to cooperate and utilize the technology that facilitates cooperation and not be stuck in paradigms for the sake of familiarity. The future rewards of competition over teamwork might also be necessary for teachers to make clear. Pedagogical activities will need to be directed at developing students' behaviors and abilities through the usage of social media instruments.

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